

Brick Making Industries in Haveri District

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Abstract: Industrialization is an effective instrument of economic growth and welfare of the people of an economy. Industrial development is necessary to bring about structural changes in the economy. Karnataka is one of the leading industrial states of India. Karnataka is one of the high economic growth states in India with the expected GSDP Growth of 8.2% in the fiscal year 2010-11. Haveri is one of the seven newly formed districts in the state constituted vide govt of Karnataka Notification RD.LRD.87(Part-III) dated 20.8.1997. Haveri district has seven Talukas, Haveri, Hirekerur, Ranibennur, Byadgi, Savanur, Hangal, Shiggaon Talukas. In the Case Study selected only three Talukas such as, Haveri, Shiggaon Talukas. Now day Bricks industries has played a dominant role in the Indian economy. Day by day the demand for bricks was increasing. Each and every person has to think that he must be built up his own dream house, because of that bricks industries were established even in rural areas. The bricks industry also comes under small scale industry.

Index Terms – Brick Making Industry, Economic Growth

I. INTRODUCTION:

Clay is workable when wet and can be moulded to any shape. A brick is made by wetting clay, pressing it into a mould, which creates blocks. The processing of making bricks generally consists of following steps: Gathering, Crushing, Grinding, Screening and mixing. The raw materials producing the brick.

The brick is building material used to make walls, pavements and other elements in masonry Construction. Traditionally, the term brick referred to a unit composed of clay, but it is now used to denote any rectangular units laid in mortar. A brick can be composed clay – bearing soil, sand and lime, concrete materials. Bricks are produced in numerous classes, types materials, which vary with region and time period, and are produced in bulk quantities. Two basic categories of bricks are fired and non fired bricks, small scale industries has emerged as the most dynamic sector of the Indian industrial economy. Small scale industries constitute the key link in the process of socio economic transformation of under developed social structures.

The positive economic strategy in India as the part of the mixed economy paradigm accorded as a vital role of the small scale industry.. The nature of unemployment prevailing in developing countries is serious to that of developed nations of the world.

The developing countries like India are facing structural unemployment arising from high rate of growth of population and slow economic growth. The goal of development to provide opportunity to advance individual and community life V.K.R.V Rao points out, development is not merely the provision of opportunities but also their actual utilisation by the people for whom they are intended to administer by the government planning.

Unemployment indicates a situation where the total number of job vacancies is much less than the total number of job seekers in the country. Under the situation of unemployment, the unemployed persons do not find any gainful work in spite of having willingness and capacity to work.

The nature of unemployment in India is differs from the one that prevails in advanced countries. The underdeveloped or developing countries like India are facing structural unemployment arising from high rate of growth of population and slow economic growth, and disguised unemployment in the rural sector. A high rate of unemployment in rural areas is expected to accelerate migration to urban areas and it is likely to increase the pressure on limited infrastructure. There are several causes of large-scale unemployment in India. The important among them are: (a) Excessive growth of population, (b) Inappropriate educational system, (c) Slow growth process, (d) Increase in labor force, (e) Lack of infrastructural facilities, (f) Immobility of labor, (g) Emphasis on capital intensive projects, (h) Neglect of small and cottage industries (i) Growing number of large scale industries etc.,. It is a widespread problem affecting almost every segment of the society.

The small scale units have been contributing to higher value addition. The value added per rupee of fixed investment in a small unit is 0.96 as against 0.41 in large unit. production per unit of investment in a small scale is estimated to be 5.60 as against 1.80 in a large scale units 3.

The present study *An Economic Analysis of the Brick Making Industries - A Case Study of Haveri District* is based on the following objectives.

II. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

1. To Highlight the Brick Making Industries in Haveri District
2. To study the employment generation of the bricks industries.
3. To study the cost- benefit analysis of the brick of industries.

III. HYPOTHESIS:

The objectives of the present study, a set of hypotheses has been arrived at as follows:

1. Brick industries give more employment opportunities.
2. Most of the brick industries were established in rural area.

There different Talukas and the three categories of entrepreneurs shows in the following table no 1.1.

Table No 1.1: Selection of Respondents (Entrepreneurs)

Sl No	Taluku	Respondents (Entrepreneurs)			
		Small	Medium	Big	Total
1	Byadagi	03	03	03	09
2	Ranebennur	03	03	03	09
3	Shiggaon	03	03	03	09
Total		09	09	09	27

Thus 03 entrepreneurs from each category small, medium, big and each categories from each the three taluku Byadagi, Ranebennur and Shiggaon have been finalized for the field survey of the entrepreneurs part of the study. Thus a total of 27 entrepreneurs have been selected for the present research work.

There different taluku and the three categories of entrepreneurs

Classification of Respondents on the Basis of Production Categories and shows in the following:

Table No 1.2: Classification of Respondents on the Basis of Production Categories

Sl. No.	Taluks	Small	Medium	Big	Total
		No & %	No & %	No & %	No & %
1	Byadgi	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	09 (33.33)
2	Ranibennur	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	09 (33.33)
3	Shiggaon	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	03 (11.11)	09 (33.33)
Total		09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	27 (100.00)

Source: Primary data based on field survey.

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Thus 03 entrepreneurs from each category small, medium, big and each categories from each the three taluks Byadagi, Ranebennur and Shiggaon have been finalised the three categories of entrepreneurs **Classification of Respondents on the Basis of Production Categories** entrepreneurs part of the study. Thus a total of 27 entrepreneurs have been selected for the present research work.

Three different taluks and the three **Classification of Entrepreneur on The Basis of Cost of Production** and shows in the following:

Table No: 1.3 Classification of Entrepreneur on The Basis of Cost of Production

Sl. No.	Cost of Production	Small	Medium	Big	Total
		No & %	No & %	No & %	No & %
1	Low	01 (03.70)	01 (03.70)	00 (00.00)	02 (07.41)
2	Manageable	03 (11.11)	04 (14.81)	05 (18.52)	12 (44.44)
3	Very High	05 (18.52)	04 (14.81)	04 (14.81)	13 (48.15)
Total		09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	27 (100.00)

Source: Primary data based on field survey.

Source: Primary data based on field survey.

Thus 03 entrepreneurs from each category small, medium, big and each categories from each the three Talukas Byadagi, Ranebennur and Shiggaon have been finalized the three categories of entrepreneurs and three **Classification of Entrepreneur on The Basis of low, manageable, very high Cost of Production** entrepreneurspart of the study. Thus a total of 27 entrepreneurs have been selected for the present research work.

Three Classification of Entrepreneur on the Basis of Profit Margin and shows in the following Table No 1.4:

Sl. No.	Profit Margins	Small	Medium	Big	Total
		No & %	No & %	No & %	No & %
1	Low	06 (22.22)	04 (14.81)	02 (07.41)	12 (44.44)
2	Satisfactory	03 (11.11)	04 (14.81)	06 (22.22)	13 (48.15)
3	High	00 (00.00)	01 (03.70)	01 (03.70)	02 (07.41)
Total		09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	09 (33.33)	27 (100.00)

Source: Primary data based on field survey

Thus 03 entrepreneurs from each category small, medium, big and each categories from each the three taluks Byadagi, Ranebennur and Shiggaon have been finalized the three categories of entrepreneurs and three **Classification of Entrepreneur on the Basis of low, satisfactory high Profit Margin Entrepreneurs** part of the study. Thus a total of 27 entrepreneurs have been selected for the present research work.

The Concept of rural development is Comprehensive it involves:

1. Provision of opportunities to the rural force into the main stream of economic activity.
2. Rightful Utilization of abundant manpower through proper man power planning.
3. Realizing the creative energies of the rural people-by recognizing the different skills of the people.
4. Checking the drift of rural population to cities.
5. Enhancing participation of rural women and young people in the rural development process.
6. Improving the Quality of life of the rural people through integration between development process and environment possibilities.

IV. CONCLUSION:

Development of micro and small enterprises prevents concentration of industries at only a few places as it disperses them all over the country. It will lead to a balanced regional growth. Some studies reported that small scale is more efficient in terms of labour productivity, total factor productivity and employment potentiality. Cottage and small scale industries are simple and are operated with limited capital. This in turn increases their income-levels and quality of life. Thus, The small-scale industries helpful to increase the living standard of the people to sustain their life and fulfilment of their needs and in reducing poverty in the country.

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